

The Role and Importance of Folk Pedagogy in the Education of Students

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Abstract: This article describes the role and importance of folk pedagogy in the education of students, touches upon the issues of instilling in the minds and hearts of students the rich experience gained as a result of the vital activity of our people in different periods, their views and conclusions about moral, educational, and spiritual maturity.

Keywords: history, education, upbringing, Avesta, morality, etiquette, enlightenment, culture, traditions, national values, national customs, tradition, song, riddle, proverb, ethnology, ethnography, ethnopsychology, ethnopedagogy, value research, antiquities (archeology), spiritual studies.

It is known from history that our people not only created a unique school in the field of education, but also became great educators. We know that even when Zoroastrianism prevailed in our land, there were certain pedagogical views, and we know Zoroastrianism from the content of some pages of the sacred book "Avesta" that have come down to us. The cultural and educational development of our people has been formed, developed, and improved over the centuries. These processes have found their expression in folk pedagogy.

Folk pedagogy expresses the rich experience, moral, educational, and spiritual maturity of our people accumulated as a result of their life activities in different periods, their views and conclusions on moral, educational, and spiritual maturity. Folk pedagogy covers all areas of ethnology, ethnography, ethnopsychology and ethnopedagogy, value studies, archaeology, folklore, and folk oral art. It studies the moral and educational ideas in them. Folk pedagogy, which summarizes the advanced moral ideas and experience that have emerged in the process of educating thousands of generations over the centuries, is of great importance not only as a historical and cultural value, but also in improving the modern education system. At a time when the socio-economic, spiritual and educational changes taking place in our society require an increase in the level of professional and pedagogical training of teachers, the scientific study, thorough analysis and implementation of folk pedagogy, which reflects the pedagogical views and ideas created by our people in education, national morals, traditions, national values, and their transfer to students and young people, to the next generation, is the most important and urgent issue of our time.

Educating people, including students and youth, in all aspects is an age-old dream of humanity, especially enlighteners, and our ancestors searched for ways, laws and regulations on how to teach enlightenment and culture to the younger generation, to lead them to perfection. Raising

an enlightened and spiritually perfect person is the main goal of the discipline "Uzbek People's Pedagogy".

Today, reforms are being implemented in our country at the level of state policy in the field of education. In this regard, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev, in his address to the parliament, emphasized the need to develop a national idea that will be a source of strength for us in implementing the grand tasks set before us. In particular, we need to understand our national identity, study the ancient and rich history of our homeland, strengthen scientific research in this regard, and comprehensively support the activities of scientists in the humanitarian field. The assessment of the past must be objective, and most importantly, free from various ideological views. In this regard, we must not forget that it is the duty of each of us to develop national morals and ethics in students, to put national customs and various traditions in their place, to further develop national values, and to educate students and youth to be deeply knowledgeable and educated for the great future of the people.

Uzbek folk pedagogy has created a unique higher school in the field of education. Uzbek culture, the theory and practice of oriental national education are nourished by historical roots that go back to ancient times.

Our ancestors advised, "If life itself cannot give a person education, no teacher can teach him." This requires that a person should receive education and upbringing through his own thinking, master the norms of morality, and embody the spiritual and moral skills and competencies characteristic of the society in which he lives, the behavior of humanity.

Folk pedagogy is a science that studies human education, its formation, and the assimilation of social norms, which is an important process in social life and the development of society. It collects, generalizes, systematizes and applies ancient methods of upbringing, songs, riddles, proverbs and games of the people to the educational process. The task and subject of folk pedagogy are also based on this goal.

Folk pedagogy is to form and expand the pedagogical thinking of future pedagogical personnel, to familiarize them with the rich spiritual and educational heritage and pedagogical views, educational and educational opportunities accumulated by our people on the organization of the educational process and the theory of upbringing.

Folk pedagogy is the study of the rich experience of our people in education, methods of upbringing, human qualities and values, oriental and Turkic traditions of folk pedagogy, the expression of educational processes in folk oral literature, national customs, religious teachings, and explaining its content and essence to the future generation, as well as to students and young people.

Folk pedagogy reveals important aspects of the family in upbringing. The role of parents in the family, the relationship of children to them, raising children in the spirit of confidence in the power of their fathers, teaching them to appreciate the incomparable work of the mother, have always been effective in upbringing.

At this point, it is appropriate to look at the history of folk pedagogy. Great educators paid more attention to the pedagogical experiences of the people. Because folk pedagogy enriches the science of upbringing and serves as a basis for it.

The great educator Ya. A. Comenius also began his career by collecting material about folk oral literature, its traditions, and values.

Kh.Kh. Niyazi defines it as "The science of pedagogy was formed and developed at the core of folk pedagogy." He also mentions that the Uzbek people have created a unique system in the field of education. In his opinion, folk education is of great importance in the historical formation of the people. We should also say that folk pedagogy found its expression in Hamza's stories, dramas, plays and narratives. The decisive role of folk pedagogy in the fate of citizens

and the Motherland, which has been formed, developed and enriched over the centuries, is due, firstly, to its vitality, impact, multifacetedness, and meaning, secondly, to its creation and living directly by the people in living traditions in the process of existing life, its coverage of human problems, its focus on solving the most pressing issues of education, and thirdly, to its universal direction, universal idea - goals.

Through folk pedagogy, students and young people form and develop concepts and views such as benefiting from the teachings of thinkers and scientists and applying them to the educational process, loyalty to values, traditions, customs, learning, appreciating teachers, achieving family strength, love for the people, love for life, and obedience to national moral standards.

Students and young people need to deeply analyze, research, and thoroughly study the rich experience of the Uzbek people, being proud of the achievements of their ancestors and ancestors in today's era. This creates a sense of pride in the work of their ancestors and their lineage in students and young people. It creates a foundation for the development of national education in students and young people.

Today, great attention is paid to the study of "Folk Pedagogy" in our country. In particular, the study of folk pedagogy is necessary for teachers, teachers of general secondary schools, students of higher educational institutions, doctoral candidates and masters.

Students studying at universities and pedagogical higher educational institutions have the opportunity to study Uzbek folk pedagogy for the following purposes. firstly, as a citizen of the Republic of Uzbekistan, they acquire the principles of national ideology. Secondly, as a specialist, they develop the skills to explain the national idea and the essence of national ideology to the younger generation.

Each person, people and nation has its own dreams and spiritual views. Among them, the need for education and upbringing occupies a special place. Because every healthy person has a need to constantly acquire knowledge. In fact, only a person with a wide range of thoughts and an educated person feels free and happy.

Any state chooses a social system that is appropriate for the stage of development of its people. The state's educational system is aimed at fulfilling the social order of the system chosen by society.

As a priority direction for teaching "folk pedagogy" to students and youth, it would be appropriate to state the following in conclusion:

- Today, modern national pedagogy relies on the ideas of folk pedagogy to enrich its content and essence, to increase its impact on the formation of a person. Folk pedagogy is the main source in the education of students and youth with its folk methods, rules and principles.
- "People's Pedagogy" is a deep study of our pedagogical history from the most ancient times to the present day, an analysis of the heritage of great thinkers in the light of the present era, research on the basis of spiritual values, the incorporation of our people's experience in education into national pedagogy, the creation of a methodology for its use;
- "People's Pedagogy" is a development of society based on the mentality of our people, national ideology, the specific characteristics of a market economy, the requirements of a strong democratic legal state and an open civil society, the development of spiritual potential, the preparation of each generation for a happy life in the conditions of the 21st century.
- improving educational methods, creating pedagogical technology based on the national educational model;
- achieving harmony of nationality and universality in the content of education and studying and popularizing the national values of the peoples of the world in cooperation;

- improving general methods of education, creating a methodology for applying the experience of the peoples of the East in education, humanizing the content and methods of education;
- Enrichment with national and universal values to improve the spiritual and moral content. Creation of a technology for applying the oriental model method in moral education. Development of a theory and popular methodology for moral education in the community and in the family;
- Improving the methods of applying advanced experiences and modern pedagogical technologies used in the didactic process in the educational practice of developed foreign countries in the process of teaching folk pedagogy to students and youth;
- Folk pedagogy is the formation of personal competence qualities in future specialists through the education of students and youth.

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